

CIVIL LAW REGULATION OF TRADE RELATIONS ON THE INTERNET: THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL ASPECTS

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Abstract. *Civil regulation of trade relations via the Internet is founded on the principles of legality, fairness, and equality, which are the basis of modern legal systems. E-commerce is governed by civil law norms that address contract formation and execution, protection of parties' rights, authentication, data security, and dispute resolution. The development of online trade highlights the need for improved legal frameworks that account for the specifics of the digital environment, ensuring stability in economic relations and the protection of participants' rights.*

Keywords: *civil law, internet trade, e-commerce, legal regulation, digital environment, consumer rights, electronic transactions.*

Civil law regulation of trade relations via the Internet follows from the foundations of the legal system and principles of civil law aimed at ensuring legality, fairness and equality of participants in economic relations. Electronic commerce, which has become an integral part of modern economic activity, is subject to the norms of civil law, which determine the rights and obligations of the parties, the procedure for concluding and executing contracts, as well as mechanisms for protecting the rights and interests of participants in trade relations.

In the context of civil law, trade via the Internet is regulated by a set of normative legal acts, including laws, codes and special legislative acts aimed at regulating electronic commerce. The basis of civil law regulation of Internet trade are the principles of freedom of contract, equivalence of the parties, freedom of entrepreneurship and protection of consumer rights, which determine the conditions for concluding and executing contracts on the Internet.

In addition, civil law regulation of trade relations via the Internet takes into account the specifics of the electronic environment and the features of electronic transactions. This includes issues of authentication of the parties, the use of electronic signatures, protection of information and data privacy, as well as mechanisms for settling disputes arising within the framework of Internet trade.

Thus, civil law regulation of trade relations via the Internet is an integral part of the legal system aimed at ensuring the stability and development of electronic commerce, as well as protecting the rights and interests of all participants in online trade.

In the 20th century, society underwent significant changes. The main one for most countries can be called the transition from industrial development, in which the leading was industry, to post-industrial. The new post-industrial society has shifted towards the service sector, put information at the forefront, making its source - the Internet - one of the most necessary resources of our time [1].

Since the end of the last century, information progress on the Internet has been considered a promising direction; over the years, it has developed many times faster than predicted rates, covering an increasing number of areas. Such a revolutionary impact has affected people's lifestyle, their education and work, as well as the interaction of state authorities and local

governments on the one hand, and civil society on the other. In this regard, the state has a need to regulate processes and relations on the Internet.

According to A.S. Anisimova, today the formation of a digital economy and its legal regulation are on the agenda of both developed and developing countries. The latest technologies are increasingly penetrating the sphere of public administration, more and more companies are moving online, which is why the study of civil law regulation of relations on the Internet is a relevant topic for analysis [2].

For legal science, the need to study relations on the Internet in connection with social relations regulated by law is more relevant than ever. It is necessary to determine the presence or absence of changes in these relations, which, developing when their participants use the Internet, may require changes to existing legislation.

The process of forming conceptual categories in the sphere of legal regulation of the use of the Internet is objectively determined by the technological nature of the Internet. The dual nature of the Internet (technical and social) is reflected in the forms of legal consolidation of key concepts at the level of national and international law, as well as in determining their content and terminological use. The logic of the development of legal regulation of relations in the studied area is objectively associated with the harmonization of key conceptual categories at the level of national law, which can become the legal basis for their unification at the international legal level [3].

According to L.L. Latypova, a civil legal relationship on the Internet is an informational relationship related to the subject of civil law, the participants of which are legally equal. However, the Internet itself is not a legal entity, and, therefore, it cannot fulfill the role of a subject of legal relations. Normative legal acts regulating legal relations only on the Internet do not exist in any state today; there are only specific rules regulating certain aspects of the functioning of this network [4].

Despite all the advantages of the electronic method of concluding transactions, in practice there are many problems. As A.S. Mikayeva notes: "One of the main problems when concluding transactions electronically is determining the place where the contract was drawn up [5]". In addition, there are problems with proving the fact of concluding a transaction. It is difficult to determine the safety and immutability of the contract data, to establish the fact that the document comes from a party to the contract. Preserving the confidentiality of data, i.e. protecting it from hacking by hackers, also creates a problem.

However, one of the main problems associated with concluding transactions electronically today is the lack of a separate regulatory legal act that would regulate the procedure and order of concluding transactions in the Internet space. According to S.N. Petrov: "The development of legislation in the sphere of relations on the Internet is at an initial level, which indicates the absence of separate regulatory legal acts to regulate this institution [6]".

Based on the above, we need to study the relevant terminology in this area, including know-how terms that are widely used in civil law relations when conducting trade on the Internet.

Trade is the process of exchanging goods or services between individuals or businesses, often for the purpose of making a profit.

The Internet is a global network of information and communication technologies that allows users to exchange information, communicate and access various resources through special platforms and technologies.

Online trading is a type of trading carried out via the Internet, where the platform for selling real objects (such as stores, markets, etc.) is replaced by Internet platforms.

Online trading is the process of buying and selling goods or services over the Internet using electronic platforms, websites, mobile applications or other online communication channels. This type of trading allows buyers and sellers to make transactions in real time, exchange information about products, make online payments and deliver goods or provide services remotely.

Trade relations are relationships between trade entities, including producers, suppliers, consumers and other participants who interact in the trade process.

E-commerce is the use of information and communication technologies to conduct online transactions, provide services, sign electronic contracts, exchange information and other activities via the Internet or specialized electronic platforms.

Trade entities are participants in trade relations, such as manufacturers, suppliers, consumers, retailers, wholesalers, as well as platforms and intermediaries associated with the trade process.

When studying the trade relations on the Internet, we should analyze the right to conduct trade relations and conclude transactions. The right to conduct trade is a legal provision that grants a person or company the right to carry out commercial activities, including the sale of goods or services. This right can be granted by government agencies on the basis of legislation and is regulated by various legal norms.

The right to trade may include various aspects such as licensing, business registration, obtaining permits for certain types of activities, compliance with safety and hygiene requirements, payment of taxes and compliance with other regulations established by law.

This right is usually regulated by local laws and may vary depending on the location of the business, the type of goods or services, and the legal status of the person or company. Obtaining the right to trade may require certain procedures, permits, or mandatory registration in accordance with local rules and regulations.

Speaking about online trade, it is important to note that these legal relations are related to economic human rights, where one party provides goods or services for a certain reward, and the other party, paying the reward, acquires the goods or services. As far as we know, in the 11th century, the fourth generation of human rights appeared, in connection with the widespread use and distribution of the Internet, a generation of digital human rights appeared, which implies the transition of some of our rights from the real world to the virtual world. Thus, trade, which was previously carried out in markets, shops, stores and many other special places, began to transform into the virtual world. Based on this, we can conclude that trade is related to economic human rights. In turn, online trade also refers to economic human rights with a combination of digital human rights.

It is worth mentioning that online trade can be studied not only in the context of civil law relations, but also in the context of such rights as: financial law, business law, tax law, entrepreneurial law, international private law. In addition, from the point of view of the economic foundations of trade relations (for example, minimizing the indicators of the shadow economy), or from the point of view of ensuring human rights and freedoms in the virtual world by law enforcement agencies (for example, preventing cybercrimes on the Internet), as well as from the point of view of information communication technologies that provide access to the Internet (for example, data centers, creation of Internet platforms, website design , etc.)

In turn, this right can be called a complex right, since at one and the same moment, trade on the Internet absorbs several human rights simultaneously. For example, being a person engaged in trade on the Internet, this person simultaneously enjoys several rights, such as:

the right to engage in entrepreneurial activity;

the right to access the Internet;

the right to use the Internet;

the right to access, use and disseminate information;

the right to freedom of choice;

the right to a quality product or service;

the right to appeal;

the right to restore violated rights;

and other rights related to trade on the Internet between subjects of trade relations.

As we see, each right is very closely interconnected with each other and the absence of one of the above-mentioned rights turns this type of trade on the Internet into something else, in connection with which we conclude that the right to trade on the Internet is a complex human right.

Now that we have figured out the essence of online trade, we should find out who is the subject of these legal relations. In jurisprudence, considering the sphere of trade relations on the Internet, the key subjects are various categories of legal entities and individuals whose activities are interconnected and regulated by many regulations and standards. In detailing these subjects, the following groups can be distinguished:

Sellers (or suppliers)

Legal entities are commercial organizations registered in accordance with the established procedure and carrying out trading activities via the Internet. These include companies that use their own online stores, as well as those who sell through marketplaces and auction platforms.

Individual entrepreneurs are individuals registered as entrepreneurs without forming a legal entity, who can also sell goods and services via the Internet.

Individuals - citizens who are not registered as entrepreneurs but who participate in electronic trade relations, for example, through P2P (peer-to-peer) platforms such as online auctions and classifieds sites. Their activities may be governed by special rules and regulations.

Buyers (or consumers)

Individuals are private consumers who purchase goods or services for personal, family, household or other use not related to entrepreneurial activity. Their rights and obligations are regulated by both national and international legislation.

Legal entities and individual entrepreneurs - when purchasing goods and services for the implementation of their business activities. They are subject to the general rules of civil law, as well as specialized rules concerning e-commerce and corporate purchases.

Payment systems and financial institutions

Banks are traditional financial institutions that facilitate electronic payments and transfers between buyers and sellers. Banking activities in the field of electronic commerce are regulated by banking legislation and Central Bank regulations.

Electronic payment systems are specialized companies providing online payment services, such as PayPal, WebMoney, Yandex.Money. Their activities are regulated by the legislation on the national payment system and relevant regulations.

Processing companies are organizations that process payment transactions and ensure their security. They can provide services to both banks and electronic payment systems, as well as directly to merchants.

Internet platforms (or marketplaces)

Electronic trading platforms are platforms that provide infrastructure for trading goods and services on the Internet, such as Amazon, eBay, AliExpress. They act as intermediaries, ensuring the convenience and security of transactions.

Advertisement platforms - sites that provide users with the opportunity to post information about the sale of goods and services, such as Avito, OLX. They are usually not involved in direct settlements between the buyer and seller, but can provide additional services to increase the security of transactions.

Regulatory and supervisory authorities

National regulatory authorities are government agencies that develop and monitor the implementation of regulations in the field of electronic commerce.

International organizations are structures that develop international standards and recommendations for electronic commerce, such as the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), the International Chamber of Commerce (ICC).

Additional subjects

Logistics companies are organizations that ensure the delivery of goods from the seller to the buyer. Their activities are regulated by transport legislation and specialized standards in the field of logistics.

Service providers are companies that specialize in data protection and cybercrime prevention in the e-commerce sector. They develop and implement information security measures that meet international standards.

Thus, the legal analysis of subjects of trade relations on the Internet requires taking into account many factors and legal norms regulating their interaction. This includes civil, commercial, financial and information law, as well as norms of international law and standards developed by intergovernmental organizations.

REFERENCES

1. Samiyeva, G. (2024). Ijtimoiy sohada maqsadli jamg 'armalar va ijtimoiy fondlar faoliyatini takomillashtirishning xorij tajribasi. *THE INNOVATION ECONOMY*, 2(02).
2. Самиева, Г. Т. (2024). Анализ Бытового Обслуживания В Республике Узбекистан. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 51, 167-171.
3. Самиева, Г. Т. (2024). РАЗВИТИЕ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ ИНФРАСТРУКТУРЫ СЛУЖИТ ПОВЫШЕНИЮ БЛАГОСОСТОЯНИЯ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ. *Экономика и социум*, (5-1 (120)), 1597-1600.
4. Fayziyeva, S., Samiyeva, G., & Yuldosheva, S. (2024). Possibilities of using economic mechanisms when organizing fruit and vegetable cooperatives. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 539, p. 02024). EDP Sciences.
5. Samiyeva, G. (2023). AHOLI TURMUSH DARAJASINI OSHIRISH ISLOHOTLARINI AMALGA OSHIRISHNING XORIJ TAJRIBASI. *THE INNOVATION ECONOMY*, 1(03).
6. Samiyeva, G. T. (2023). IJTIMOYIY FONDLAR VA MAQSADLI JAMG 'ARMALAR FAOLIYATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.

7. Samiyeva, G. (2023). O 'ZBEKISTONDA OZIQ-OVQAT XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASH ISTIQBOLLARI. THE INNOVATION ECONOMY, 1(02), 35-49.
8. Rasulovna, N. Z. (2024). Some Aspects of Organizing and Improving Students' Oral Speech at Non-Language Faculties. Miasto Przyszłości, 49, 373-375.
9. Nazirova, Z. (2023). METHODS OF MEASUREMENT OF CORNEA DIAMETER IN CHILDREN. Science and innovation, 2(D12), 482-485.
10. Nazirova, Z. (2023). IMPROVING THE USE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE TO VETERINARY STUDENTS. Science and innovation, 2(B7), 218-220.
11. Zilola, N. (2022). XORIJIY TILLARNI O 'QITISHDA PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALARNING AHAMIYATI (RUS TILI MISOLIDA). ILMIY TADQIQOT VA INNOVATSIYA, 1(1), 188-192.
12. Nazirova, Z. R. THE MANAGEMENT ALGORITHM OF CHILDREN WITH REFRACTORY GLAUCOMA. Impact Factor: 4.9, 11.
13. Назирова, З. Р. (2021). THE MANAGEMENT ALGORITHM OF CHILDREN WITH REFRACTORY GLAUCOMA. УЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ, (SPECIAL 1).
14. Rasulovna, N. Z. (2021, April). APPLICATION OF VIDEO MATERIALS IN THE FORMATION OF COMPETENCE OF VETERINARY STUDENTS IN THE STUDY OF THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE. In Archive of Conferences (Vol. 18, No. 1, pp. 37-38).
15. Khamidova, M. A., & Orifkhonova, N. O. (2024). THE IMPORTANCE OF MICRO AND MACROELEMENTS IN MICROCLONAL PROPAGATION OF POTATOES. СОВРЕМЕННОЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ И ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ, 1(1), 195-197.
16. Bo'ronov, N. (2024). MEDIA SAVODXONLIKNI OSHIRISHDA VR LABORATORIYANING TASHKILY MODUL MEKANIZMI. TAMADDUN NURI JURNALI, 5(56), 454-457.
17. Nazim, B. R. (2022). O'zbek tilshunosligida takror va uning uslubiy xususiyatlari ba'zi adabiyotlarda, ayrim tadqiqot ishlarida o'rganilgan. Erkin Vohidov ijodida doston janri alohida ahamiyatga ega. Mazkur maqolada Erkin Vohidov "Nido" dostonining til xususiyatlari haqida so. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON LEARNING AND TEACHING, 1(3), 500-504.
18. Бурунов, Н., & Шоғуломов, Д. (2020). PREVENTING INFORMATION HAZARDS IN ONLINE PUBLICATIONS ПРЕДОТВРАЩЕНИЕ. ББК 60 Е244 Ответственный редактор: Гуляев Герман Юрьевич, кандидат экономических наук Е244, 24.
19. Bo'ronov, N. M., & Nurutdinova, M. (2019). XXI ASRDA DINIY EKSTREMIZM TAHDIDLARI. In WORLD SCIENCE: PROBLEMS AND INNOVATIONS (pp. 289-290).